

Separation of some Purines and Pyrimidines by Thin Layer Chromatography using Heulandite as an Adsorbent

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In our earlier communication¹, we gave the introduction to heulandite, a zeolite. Using the same zeolite, we report in this communication some purines and pyrimidine migration and their separation.

Results and Discussion

R_f values obtained (Table 1) for different purines and pyrimidines on heulandite, silica gel G and H layer, and for quaternary mixtures are given in Table 1. It is possible to separate many binary and ternary combinations.

TABLE 1— R_f VALUES OF PURINES, PYRIMIDINES AND THEIR MIXTURES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Heulandite	Silica gel G	Silica gel H
1.	Adenine	0.96	0.98	0.31
2.	Guanine	0.82	0.87 ^a	0.91
3.	Thymine	0.96	0.53 ^a	0.30
4.	Cytosine	0.88	0.57 ^a	0.41 ^a
5.	Uracil	0.80	0.74 ^a	0.62 ^a
6.	Adenosine	0.00	0.89 ^a	0.31
7.	Hypoxanthine	0.64	0.91 ^a	0.30
Mixture :				
1.	Adenine + guanine + hypoxanthine + adenosine	0.96 0.83 0.64 0.00	NS	NS
2.	Cytosine + uracil + hypoxanthine + adenosine	0.89 0.80 0.64 0.00	NS	NS
3.	Thymine uracil + hypoxanthine + adenosine	0.96 0.80 0.64 0.00	NS	NS
4.	Thymine + guanine + hypoxanthine + adenosine	0.96 0.82 0.64 0.00	NS	NS

^aSmall tailing on the spot. NS = no separation.

In tlc, migration of a molecule depends on the strength of the interaction between the adsorbent and the polar groups of the molecule. The more polar the groups, the stronger is the interaction and slower will be the migration². This is best expressed by placing the functional groups in their order of affinity for the adsorbent: OH > C=O > NH₂. Applying this rule to purines and pyrimidines and observing their functional groups the following sequence is made: adenosine > hypoxanthine > guanine > adenine. Since adenosine showed more polarity (with 3 OH groups) the migration is zero (Table 1) and adenine showed less polarity (1 NH₂ group) hence higher will be the migration. The same trend is followed with the purines: uracil > cytosine > thymine. Since uracil has high polarity due to presence of two keto groups lesser will be the R_f value compared to others. Thymine is less polar than cytosine due to presence of a methyl group, so the R_f value is higher than cytosine.

Experimental

Characterisation of the sample and preparation of chromatoplates were the same as reported earlier¹.

Standard solutions were prepared by dissolving each compound (0.05 g) in 0.1% KOH (100 ml).

Chromatographic procedure : The spot solu-

tions of purines and pyrimidines and their different combinations (containing 3.0–3.5 μg sample) were spotted on the chromatoplates using microcapillary tubes. The chromatoplates were then developed by ascending technique upto a distance of 4–5 cm within 6 min using solvent water (pH 11). The plates were dried, cooled and kept in an

iodine chamber to develop brown colour to the spots.

References

1. B. SRINIVAS and K. SRINIVASULU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 669.
2. H. BROCKMANN and F. VOLPERS, *Chem. Ber.*, 1949, **82**, 95.